

SUCCESS STORY

One Stop Solution to All Your Farming Needs

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Mr. Amit Kumar, resident from West Champaran district, Bihar. He Graduated from Agriculture in 2015 from Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agriculture University. He worked as an advisor in Kisan Call Center. In 2017 he left the Kisan Call Center. In 2018 along with some agri start up work did MBA in Rural Management from Dr. Rajendra Prasad Central Agriculture University. And at the same time, on 17 April 2020, with the guidance of professor, he put project in Bihar Start-up. He contacted DMI Patna for the establishment of incubation centre on 18 August 2020, but due to Corona protocol, incubation started from December 2020 and got certified on 4 June 2021. On April 2021 he joined Assistant Technician Manager Atma Shivhar District but left the job in December 2021. In the initial phase of agri start-up journey except his family members and friends, society started seeing him as a shopkeeper but never losses hope and distracted from his ambition. Mr. Amit Kumar founder of Pusanow Farmers Solution Pvt. Ltd. (**One stop solution to all your farming needs**) provides a platform to farmers of remote villages in Bihar in accessing, understanding and adopting modern methods of Agriculture and using inputs which will take them one rung above on the ladder of agro-economic development. All this is done by providing services to farmers at the door steps in their villages. The start up with its three-lakh initial capital three manpower earn net profit 10-12 k per month

Pusanow Farmers Solution Pvt. Ltd provides following services to farmers in remote villages in Bihar.

- Start-up provides high quality seed, fertilizer, pesticide, spray machine, green house, drip irrigation system, organic manure, vermi compost and pesticide on one stop shop along with telephone based advisory service with soil health card.
- Provide services of field officer to train farmers on modern scientific farming, high value crops like mushroom, strawberry, capsicum etc., generate demand of agri input.
- Start-up will also develop and established micro processing unit through farmers cluster of 5-10 village.
- Start-ups produce market linkage from farmer's field to market with logo Pusanow FS Pvt. Ltd.

The firm work on producing vermi composed and low-cost Nano liquid organic manure, magic product which act as both fertilizer and pesticides. Through that magic product firm can motivate farmers (mainly backyard farm) towards organic farming and online selling (door to door) organic vegetables, fruits etc.

This start-up works as a rural E-Commerce centre and provide real benefits to farmers by providing its services in terms of multiple input.

